

Interview - User-Centred Design (UCD) Lab at the University of Brighton

Authors:

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: User-Centred Design (UCD) Lab at the University of Brighton

Meeting date: 18/02/2025

[Dr Sanaz Fallahkhair](#) is based at the University of Brighton. She is a Principal Lecturer in Human Centred AI and Interaction at the School of Architecture, Technology and Engineering, University of Brighton. She leads and manages the [Brighton User Centred Design Laboratory](#) which provides Research and Consultancy in the areas of Human Centred AI, User Experience Design (UX), Product Development, and UX testing and Evaluation.

Sanaz has experience working within teaching, research and industry, both on a national and international basis. Supported 100's of student MSc projects over the years, many interested in environment, data and data visualisation contexts.

Poppy Townsend and Thomas Zwagerman met with Sanaz on Tuesday 18th February 2025 to discuss their experience in user centred design and related fields. This document provides a summary of the discussion.

Key points from our discussion

- User centred design is domain agnostic. The toolkit is an opportunity to tailor specific aspects of user centred design for the environmental science domain. Sanaz thought this was an excellent idea but wondered where/how we would like to progress this work.
- Lots of jargon in this field of work - user centred design, co-creation, participatory research, user experience... etc.
- [Human centered AI](#) is an emerging discipline intent on creating AI systems that amplify and augment rather than displace human abilities. We discussed how human centred AI could be used to benefit all aspects of user centred design. e.g. how AI could be used (alongside design thinking principles) to define personas. It would be interesting to collaborate on an environmental data project linked to this.
- Comparison of using AI and humans for user centred design work. results so we know what the differences are, and can build understanding and trust in using these new technologies.
- Barriers to collaboration: lack of funding. Additional funding would be required to explore this work further.

Areas for possible future collaborations

- Work with the Brighton User Centred Design Lab to support for user experience developments
- Human centred AI domain - co-creation (humans and AI), how AI can support user experience in the environmental science domain
- Equality, diversity and inclusion - user perspectives, accessibility of data (for users and AI)
- Education and training (for our staff)

Potential mechanisms for collaboration:

- Project partner
- Pitch an idea for MSc student projects - Oct 2025
- Host a placement student - Oct 2025

Additional projects/resources identified

- MSc course topics list -
<https://www.brighton.ac.uk/courses/study/user-experience-design-msc-pgcert-pgdip.aspx>
- Industry partners working in environmental domain - don't have any current partners in this domain but interested to explore further
- [All other publications in UCD and My profile](#) are relevant.
- Jargon buster/glossary for user centred design -
 - <https://thestandardinteractiondesignprocess.wordpress.com/>
 - <https://www.uxdesigninstitute.com/blog/glossary-ux-terms/>